

Marine ecosystem classification for surface waters of Europe

Deliverable 2.3

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The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), the Ocean University of China (China), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the University of the Ryukyus (Japan), Aarhus University (Denmark), and the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 2.3 overview

The present document details the data acquisition and computational procedures involved in Deliverable 2.3 of MPA Europe. It provides the **classification of marine ecosystems in Europe for surface waters** driven by a wide range of spatially complete and standardised environmental data that reflect both ecosystem conditions and functioning.

The classification of ecosystems considered clustering algorithms fitting high-resolution environmental data for European seas ([Environmental data preparation; Deliverable 2.1](#), WP2; Assis et al, 2023). In this scope and for the purposes of the MPA Europe project, ‘ecosystems’ are defined as “*enduring, spatially bounded environments where biological and energy interactions are greater within than with other ecosystems*” (Zhao et al. 2019). The information provided is crucial for policy-relevant research focusing on MPA designation, in particular, mapping biodiversity patterns. In particular, it will feed the main subsequent tasks of Prioritisation (WP5), which aim to design (prioritise locations for) MPA networks using a systematic conservation planning approach maximising the coverage of the marine biodiversity..

Methods

The environmental data used in cluster analysis was derived from [Deliverable 2.1](#) (WP2, Assis et al., 2023). These data comprise high-resolution (0.05 degrees, approx. 5 km at the equator), spatially complete and standardised environmental data layers for the European seas, generated with information from the Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast and the Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Analysis and Forecast, two pre-processed re-analyses of [Copernicus Marine Service](#) that integrate and assimilate a comprehensive range of satellite and in-situ data (Assis et al., 2023).

Eight meaningful environmental variables for the surface waters (0-0.5 m) of European seas were selected, namely, dissolved molecular oxygen (mmol m⁻³), nitrate (mmol m⁻³), ocean temperature (°C), pH, phosphate (mmol m⁻³), phytoplankton (mmol m⁻³), salinity, and sea ice cover (%). Data were represented as the averaged values over the decade 2010-2020, except for sea ice cover, which referred to the maximum value for the decade. Thus, the ecosystem classification reflects the long-term enduring “climatology” that drives the distribution of species and habitats as distinct from seasonal and annual variation that affect population abundance. The correlation among selected variables was assessed through the Pearson's correlation coefficient (Table 1).

Table 1. Pearson's correlation coefficient for the eight environmental variables selected: dissolved molecular oxygen (oxygen), nitrate, ocean temperature (temp.), pH, phosphate, salinity, sea ice cover (sea ice) and phytoplankton (phyto). Absolute correlation values higher than 0.70 (Dormann et al. 2013) are highlighted in **bold**.

	Oxygen	Nitrate	Temp.	pH	Phosphate	Salinity	Sea ice	Phyto.
Oxygen	1	0.75	-0.96	0.32	0.35	-0.42	0.65	0.06
Nitrate		1	-0.87	0.35	0.35	0.00	0.47	-0.03
Temp.			1	-0.41	-0.37	0.20	-0.62	-0.01
pH				1	0.71	0.05	0.35	-0.08
Phosphate					1	-0.35	0.18	0.06
Salinity						1	-0.12	-0.29
Sea ice							1	-0.33
Phyto.								1

Data were standardised using Z-scores. This procedure involved adjusting each data point to be centred on the mean and scaled based on the standard deviation. Standardisation with Z-scores is crucial for removing scale bias, ensuring an unbiased interpretation of results, and facilitating comparisons between variables.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was further performed to mitigate inter-variable correlations and reduce data dimensionality. PCA is a multivariate technique that transforms the original variables into a new set of orthogonal variable dimensions called principal components. The initial four principal components were selected, which collectively explained 91 % of the variance (Table 2). This led to a data matrix comprising 658,034 rows (i.e., linked to the 0.05 resolution cells) and four columns. By retaining these components, information was effectively captured while reducing the complexity of the dataset.

Table 2. Result of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The first four principal components (PC1-4) recovered 91 % of the variance in the data matrix (in **bold**).

	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8
Standard deviation	1.93	1.20	1.11	0.92	0.65	0.42	0.29	0.08
Proportion of variance	0.46	0.18	0.15	0.10	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.00
Cumulative proportion	0.46	0.64	0.80	0.91	0.96	0.98	0.99	1.00

K-means clustering approach was utilised to find structure in the data. This is a popular unsupervised machine learning algorithm used for partitioning a dataset into a predefined number of distinct, non-overlapping clusters. It works by iteratively assigning data points to the nearest cluster centroid and then recalculating the centroids based on the mean of the points assigned to each cluster. This process continues until convergence, when the centroids no longer change significantly. K-means algorithms seek to minimise the within-cluster sum of squared (WCSS) distances, i.e., between data points and the centroids of their respective clusters. Thus, it is suitable for clustering data points with numerical features into K clusters, where K is a user-specified parameter. It is an efficient method known for its simplicity in cluster assignment.

The appropriate number of clusters was determined using the library *NbClust* (Charrad et al. 2014) of R computing language (R Core Team, 2023). It implements and compares 30 cluster validity indices to provide the best clustering structure consensus from a range of results. Due to the substantial size of the dataset and the *NbClust* requirement to compute a distance matrix, resource limitation prevented from executing the function for the entire dataset. Instead, 100 random samples of a size of 1,000 were iteratively generated to calculate the validity indices. A dissimilarity matrix was computed for each subset using Euclidean distances to test a range from 2 to 20 possible clusters. The outcome derived from the combination of indices indicated that five clusters is the optimal choice to structure the data (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Optimal number of clusters according to the combined outcome of 30 cluster validity indices obtained from 100 random samples of 1,000 data points. K=5 was selected more often (Count) across indices and samples.

K-means clustering was then applied to the data using the *kmeans* function in R with a fixed number of clusters equal to five, as previously estimated, while considering the Lloyd's algorithm and a maximum of 10 iterations. Lloyd's algorithm is a three-step approach to minimize the within-cluster sum of squared distances. In our case, this algorithm starts by choosing five random data points as centroids (previously estimated $k = 5$). Then, it assigns all data points to their closest centroid, and finally it performs the recalculation of centroids as mean over all their assigned data points. These last two steps are repeated until the defined maximum of 100 iterations. Since the resulting clusters are heavily influenced by the choosing of initial centroids, i.e., the Lloyd's algorithm might get stuck in a local optimum, we allowed for 25 random initial centroid assignments.

Further, within the K-means method, uncertainty in the cluster assignments was estimated by incorporating fuzzy logic approach, which assigns data points to clusters based on degrees of membership. This means that data points can belong to multiple clusters with varying degrees of likelihood, allowing for the representation of uncertainty and overlapping patterns.

The Euclidean distance between clusters was calculated as the mean of all pairwise distances among the data points from different clusters. The resulting distance matrix was utilized to construct a dendrogram illustrating the hierarchical grouping of individual elements into clusters based on their relative Euclidean distances. This was achieved using the R function *hclust*, which performs agglomerative hierarchical clustering.

The clustering quality and statistical significance was inferred through four independent indices: Average Jaccard Index, Cluster Instability, Dunn Index, and Silhouette Score. These metrics, which are described in detail in Table 3, capture different aspects of cluster quality, providing a more holistic understanding of the resulting structure. Significance of indices was assessed through bootstrapping, by comparing the validation scores of the actual clustering to the distribution of scores obtained from 1,000 randomizations. This approach determines the proportion of random validation

scores that are equal to or greater than the actual validation scores. A significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was used to determine statistical significance.

Table 3. Summary of clustering validation metrics.

Metrics	Description
Average Jaccard Index	It measures the similarity between all pairs of clusters and then computes the average. It ranges from 0 to 1. Higher values indicate better-defined clusters, with 1 implying perfect cluster similarity.
Cluster Instability	It quantifies the cluster assignment sensitivity to slight changes in the data. It ranges from 0 to 1, with 0 indicating perfect stability and 1 indicating complete instability.
Dunn Index	It is the ratio of the minimum inter-cluster distance to the maximum intra-cluster distance. It theoretically ranges from 0 to infinity, however, values from 0 to 1 are more common. A higher value suggests better clustering, where clusters are more compact and well-separated from each other.
Silhouette Score	It measures how similar an object is to its own cluster (intra-cluster similarity) compared to other clusters (inter-cluster dissimilarity). It provides a way to quantify the separation between clusters and the cohesion within clusters. It ranges from -1 to +1, where -1 implies incorrect clustering, 0 suggests overlapping clusters, and 1 indicates well-defined and well-separated clusters.

Results

Five clusters were identified among the surface waters of European seas (Figure 2), with sizes (in decreasing order) of 311,706 cells (47.37 % surface, cluster 2), 222,768 cells (33.85 %, cluster 4), 80,570 cells (12.24 %, cluster 3), 24,359 cells (3.70 %, cluster 1), and 18,631 cells (2.83 %, cluster 5), at a resolution of 0.05 degrees.

The spatial distribution of the clusters was well-resolved. In detail, cluster 1 defined the Baltic Sea; cluster 2 defined the North Sea, the Northeast Atlantic and some discrete upwelling or colder regions along the Moroccan, Iberian, French northeast Adriatic and Greek coasts; cluster 3 defined the Arctic Sea; cluster 4 defined the Mediterranean and Sea and the adjacent Northeast Atlantic Ocean (including Azores Islands) and Celtic Sea; and cluster 5 defined the Black Sea (Figure 4).

Figure 4. European marine ecosystems of surface waters estimated by k-means clustering analysis of environmental data. Data aggregated into equal-area hexagons 10 km wide for representation. Colour scale defines the five distinctive clusters identified in this study.

Fuzzy logic analysis based on k-means clustering showed very high assignment precision to a single cluster. In a range of membership values between 0 (i.e., fuzzy assignment) and 1 (i.e., clear

assignment), the precision varied from 0.2 to 1, with values closed to 1 for most cells across the European seas (Figure 5). Despite the overall patterns, lower precision was mostly inferred along the transition between clusters, together with the areas of west coasts and those influenced by river runoffs, wetlands and lagoons (Figure 5). Thus, these areas include: the west coast upwelling region of Moroccan, Iberian Peninsula and France, some Mediterranean coasts, the Celtic Sea, and the southern portion of the North Sea. Areas of low precision for the Mediterranean Sea (e.g. northeast coast of France, northern Adriatic and Greek coasts), eastern coasts of Baltic Sea, and northern Black Sea could reflect temperature difference, variability and riverine and wetlands inputs (e.g. Camargue Regional Nature Park, Po Delta Park, Nesto National Park, and Ethniko Ygrotopiko Evrou Delta Park in Mediterranean Sea, respectively; Torne and Kmijoki rivers, Neva River, Daugava River, Vistula River, and Szczecin Lagoon in the Baltic Sea, respectively; Sasyk Kunduk Lagoon, Tuzlovski Lagoons National Park, Lower Dniester National Park, Pivdennyi Buh River, and Dniipro River in the Black Sea, respectively).

Figure 5. Clustering assignment precision based on fuzzy logic. Values range from 0.2 to 1 and define the precision of each cells' assignment to the respective cluster.

Hierarchical clustering analysis based on environmental distance between clusters showed distinctive cluster relationships and revealed the existence of two main groups (Figure 6). The first group included clusters 1, 3, and 5. Cluster 3 exhibited the higher differentiation within it, with a relative distance of 0.58 from clusters 1 and 5, which differed with a relative distance of 0.34. These two were the more similar clusters. On the other hand, a second group including clusters 2 and 4 showed that these clusters differed among them with a relative distance of 0.43.

Figure 6. Environmental Euclidean distance between clusters

The resultant WCSS, a measure of the variability or dispersion of data points within each cluster, was: WCSS1 = 100,842.1; WCSS2 = 425,401.5; WCSS3 = 75,047.1; WCSS4 = 101,325.7; and WCSS5 = 65,296.9, for cluster 1-5 respectively. The R² (i.e., proportion of the total variation explained by the clustering) was 84 %. Regarding the cluster validation, Dunn Index and Silhouette Score significant values of 1.31 and 0.63 respectively (Table 4), revealed a high-quality data structuring, with compact and well-defined clusters. In addition, at the cluster level, high Average Jaccard Index values (0.63-0.97) and low Cluster Instability values (0.00-0.22) were retrieved, reinforcing that clusters are well-separated, non-overlapping and distinct from each other. However, it is worth mentioning that cluster 2 had worse validation scores, suggesting that this solution can be sensitive to variations in the data or algorithm parameters (Table 4).

Table 4. Results of clustering validation metrics. *Asterisks show significant validation scores obtained from 1,000 randomizations.

	Average Jaccard Index	Cluster Instability	Dunn Index	Silhouette Score
Cluster 1	0.86	0.00	1.31 *	0.63 *
Cluster 2	0.63	0.22		
Cluster 3	0.93	0.00		
Cluster 4	0.96	0.00		
Cluster 5	0.97	0.00		

Environmental variables more correlated with other variables (temperature, oxygen, phosphate and nitrate; Table 1) contributed less unique information to the PCA. On the contrary, phytoplankton and sea ice cover were the higher contributors. However, it is important to note that all values exceeded 90 %, indicating that all variables contributed to the principal components in a very similar proportion (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Percentage of variance explained by the Principal Component Analysis after excluding each environmental variable.

The clusters were well-resolved and linked to distinct environmental characteristics (Figure 8; Table 5). In detail:

- Cluster 1 (Baltic Sea) was characterised by relatively high dissolved oxygen, low to moderate nitrate levels, average ocean temperature, slightly alkaline pH, low phosphate levels, the lowest salinity among the clusters, minimal sea ice cover, and moderate phytoplankton levels.
- Cluster 2 (NE Atlantic) exhibits lower dissolved oxygen levels, varying nitrate concentrations, a wide range of ocean temperatures, slightly alkaline pH, low to moderate phosphate levels, high salinity, minimal sea ice cover, and moderate phytoplankton levels.
- Cluster 3 (Arctic European seas) stands out with high dissolved oxygen, moderate nitrate levels, negative ocean temperatures, slightly alkaline pH, moderate phosphate levels, high salinity, significant sea ice cover, and low phytoplankton levels.

- Cluster 4 (Southern European seas) is defined by lower dissolved oxygen levels, low nitrate concentrations, high ocean temperatures, slightly alkaline pH, low phosphate levels, very high salinity, no sea ice cover, and low phytoplankton levels.
- Cluster 5 (Black Sea) is marked by moderate dissolved oxygen levels, low nitrate concentrations, high ocean temperatures, slightly alkaline pH, moderate phosphate levels, relatively low salinity, no sea ice cover, and moderate phytoplankton levels.

Figure 8. Environmental characteristics of the five identified clusters. Variables: dissolved molecular oxygen, nitrate, ocean temperature (temp), pH, phosphate, salinity, sea ice cover (sea ice) and phytoplankton (phyto). Mean of each variable in red and range (minimum and maximum) in yellow. It is important to note that the values are presented in percentages, where 0-100 % represents the full range of each variable. This approach ensures comparability among the clusters.

Table 5. Summary of the environmental characteristics of the five identified clusters. Variables: dissolved molecular oxygen, nitrate, ocean temperature (temp.), pH, phosphate, salinity, sea ice cover (sea ice) and phytoplankton (phyto). Mean of each variable and range [min, max].

	Oxygen (mmol m-3)	Nitrate (mmol m-3)	Temp. (°C)	pH	Phosphate (mmol m-3)	Salinity	Sea ice (proportion)	Phyto. (mmol m-3)
Cluster 1	356.09 [291.98, 384.05]	1.96 [0.13, 19.82]	8.60 [5.61, 14.95]	7.99 [7.25, 8.10]	0.05 [0.01, 1.08]	6.56 [1.86, 26.52]	0.18 [0.00, 0.94]	2.72 [1.49, 11.59]
Cluster 2	298.43 [225.08, 364.60]	5.04 [0.06, 21.85]	7.74 [0.18, 22.97]	8.08 [8.00, 8.25]	0.39 [0.00, 1.96]	34.80 [18.09, 38.91]	0.02 [0.00, 0.72]	2.19 [1.21, 19.38]
Cluster 3	358.50	7.12	-0.53	8.13	0.54	33.73	0.84	0.87

	[321.26, 371.69]	[1.70, -1.81]	[-1.81, 4.10]	[8.06, 8.17]	[0.25, 0.63]	[32.51, 38.64]	[0.19, 0.97]	[0.37, 2.61]
Cluster 4	233.49 [214.18, 275.34]	0.27 [0.00, 3.89]	19.57 [11.60, 23.75]	8.05 [8.03, 8.16]	0.03 [0.00, 0.79]	37.11 [30.46, 39.54]	0.00 [0.00, 0.00]	1.36 [0.92, 5.25]
Cluster 5	270.22 [249.46, 309.83]	0.31 [0.03, 11.41]	16.17 [11.44, 18.55]	8.20 [8.06, 0.54]	2.28 [0.54, 2.99]	18.07 [12.79, 34.02]	0.00 [0.00, 0.01]	2.55 [1.62, 21.35]

In summary, through selection of biologically meaningfully environmental variables, and the application of K-means clustering analysis, the current deliverable provides a robust classification of marine ecosystems in European surface waters that reflect both ecosystem conditions and functioning. This reveals five well-defined clusters, each associated with distinct environmental characteristics. These clusters provide valuable insights for policymakers and researchers, particularly in the context of marine protected area designation and biodiversity conservation. The rigorous validation metrics demonstrate the quality and reliability of the clustering results, reinforcing their significance for the MPA Europe project's objectives.

The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information (e.g. further analysis for areas of low precision) and/or adjustments (e.g. lack of representation of Marmara Sea as the data-driven limitation) may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the quality of the results and the scientific knowledge.

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